

Inventorylist_figure4

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Loading packages

```
library(ggplot2)
library(ggpubr)
library(fitdistrplus)
library(openxlsx)
library(tidyverse)
```

Get work directory and organise results

```
HOME <- "C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Focus"
setwd(HOME)
```

Create a folder with current date in the Result folder

```
newday <- file.path('C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Focus/Results',
Sys.Date())
dir.create(newday)
```

Read in data

```
Inventory_domain <-
read_delim("C:/Users/TRHU/Documents/R/PARC_VKM_Focus/Data/Trine_Figure4_new.csv")
```

Make figures

Make a long table from the summarydata

```
Inventory_domain_long <- Inventory_domain %>% pivot_longer(cols = !Domain,
names_to = "Source", values_to = "Count")

# Lock in factor level order
Inventory_domain_long$Source <- factor(Inventory_domain_long$Source, levels =
c("Cooper", "IRIS", "OHAT", "ROB2", "ROBINS-E", "SciRAP", "SR", "Focus
Groups", "All sources" ))
```

```

BiasDomain_Source <- Inventory_domain_long %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = fct_rev(Domain), y = Count, fill = fct_rev(Source))) +
  geom_col(position="dodge") +
  facet_grid( ~ Source, labeller = label_wrap_gen(width=20)) +
  coord_flip() +
  geom_text(aes(label = round(Count, 0)), size = 4, hjust = -.2) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none") +
  theme(axis.line = element_line(color='black'),
        plot.background = element_blank(),
        panel.grid.major = element_blank(),
        panel.grid.minor = element_blank()+
        #panel.border = element_blank()+
  theme(strip.text.x = element_text(face = 'bold', size = 25),
        strip.background = element_rect(fill="white", colour="black",size=1))
+
  theme(axis.title = element_text(size = 22),
        axis.text.x = element_text(face = 'bold', size = 10),
        axis.text.y = element_text(face = 'bold', size = 11),
        legend.text = element_text(size = 11),
        legend.title = element_text(size = 11),
        legend.key.size = unit(1, 'cm'),
        plot.title = element_text(size = 10),
        strip.text.x = element_text(size = 8), #change the facets font
        plot.caption = element_text(face = 'bold', size = 15),
        plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 15))+
  labs(y = "Source (# items)", x = "Bias Domain")

```

BiasDomain_Source

Bias Domain


```

ggsave(filename=file.path(newday, "BiasDomain_Source.jpeg"),
        device = NULL,
        width=NA,
        height=NA,
        units="mm")

```